

MIXED METHODS RESEARCH ON IMPLEMENTATION OF LIVELIHOOD PROGRAMS AND QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG MARGINALIZED SECTORS IN CALAMBA CITY

Jeseca M. Maranan

School of Graduate Studies, Laguna College of Business and Arts, Calamba, Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10968537>

ABSTRACT

This mixed methods study was conducted to determine the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life among marginalized sectors in Calamba City, Laguna. The study used sequential explanatory design. For the quantitative data, purposive sampling was used for 150 respondents from selected marginalized sectors who had access to different livelihood programs offered by the government. For the qualitative data, purposeful sampling was used for 10 participants to provide deeper insights into the study. Validated researcher-made survey instruments and semi-structured interview questions were used in data gathering. Using the four-point Likert scale, frequency, and mean, findings revealed that livelihood programs were implemented in marginalized sectors in terms of applicability, acceptability, marketability, and sustainability. The findings on the quality of life of marginalized sectors were satisfactory in terms of life satisfaction, affluent life, and rich life aspiration. There was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the quality of life among marginalized sectors. Using Thematic Analysis, the themes that emerged from the respondents' interviews of their lived experiences were Farming, Poultry, and Fishing Government Initiated Programs; Government Initiatives; Income and Agricultural Materials; Assistance Strategy, Adjustment Strategy, and Expansion Strategy; Farming, Fishing, and Poultry-Raising; Availability, Reliability, and Technical Efficiency; Marketing and Financial Strategies; Personal and Financial Development; and, Sustainability of Livelihood Programs and Children's Education. A livelihood program was proposed as the output of the study.

Keywords: *Implementation, Livelihood Programs, Quality of Life, Marginalized Sectors*

INTRODUCTION

Marginalization has been a prevalent issue as it is subjected to multiple forms of discrimination and exclusion in political, social, and economic life due to unequal power relationships in economic, political, and social dimensions. This has led to a vulnerability that deprives people of having a voice over their lives and available resources, identity because of limited opportunities for social and economic growth, and even place in the community.

As it is, Republic Act 8425, or the Social Reform and Poverty Alleviation Act explains the individuals and/or families who fall under the poverty threshold and those who cannot afford and sustain their basic needs such as food, health, education, housing, and other amenities in life. Families who belong to marginalized sectors include farmers and fisherfolks; minimum wage earners in the formal sector; migrant workers who experience labor and salary-related abuses; indigent people; women and people with special needs; senior citizens; victims of natural disasters and calamities; young adulthood, students, and children; poor in urban areas; members of cooperative; and those in civil society organizations.

Moreover, Republic Act No. 11291, or the Magna Carta of the Poor provided investments in anti-poverty programs to help the poor actively participate and engage in different programs and activities that accelerated their growth and potential. It also gave the marginalized full access to different governmental services; addressed the needs of vulnerable sectors; and enhanced people's competencies through the implementation of different programs and services for them.

The survey conducted by the National Economic Development Authority (NEDA) (2016) dubbed as 'Ambisyon 2040' described the kind of life Filipinos want to live, and how the country would be whereas 79% of Filipinos aspired to a simple and comfortable life, 16.9% wanted an affluent life, and 3.9% aspired for the life of the rich. The survey also aimed to 'ensure people-centered, efficient, and clean governance' to have a prosperous country where no one is left behind, the people will live longer and healthier, smart and innovative, and have a high trust in society.

This quality of life helped in addressing inequalities and recognizing the importance of marginalized sectors to increase their capacities to help themselves and their communities. Also, it gave them the power or voice in the planning and execution process to achieve the efficiency goals of development organizations.

However, marginalized sectors are prone to experience disparities and lack of empowerment making them poor, earning less, and settling for fewer opportunities. These effects, though unintended, made the marginalized sectors more passive and reliant on development aid, and reduced their voices against inequalities and discrimination in their

socioeconomic growth. That's why, the implementation of government livelihood was important as it ensured and supported changes, and increased acceptability and sustainability, especially in marginalized sectors.

Wokadala et al. (2020) described sustainable livelihood as important in poverty alleviation by surviving different shocks and stresses and improving people's quality of life on a long-term basis. It established a safety net for marginalized groups in transforming their lives through income and opportunities. To be sustainable, a combination of livelihood assets was needed to generate a positive effect in meeting the needs and sustaining their well-being.

Relatively, the study of Sackey and Remoaldo (2019) about livelihood empowerment against poverty was set to measure the intended impacts of programs on beneficiaries, especially in reducing extreme poverty among poor populations, increasing active participation in education, and empowerment in acquiring skills and resources to break the inter-generational cycle. The programs unraveled the irregularities encountered by beneficiaries in proffering policy directions in addressing the issue of poverty.

It is in this regard that the researcher, being one of the employees of the Gender and Development Office (GADO) became interested in pursuing this study. Knowing the stories of marginalized sectors who have experienced lesser access to opportunities, drove the researcher to conduct further study to serve as a living witness of the current situation of the status of these sectors in terms of accessing different livelihood programs from the government. The knowledge of marginalized sectors regarding livelihoods helped create changes in people's potential and their socio-economic growth.

Moreover, the study discerned the relationship of implemented livelihood programs on marginalized sectors in terms of improving their lives, generating additional sources of income, and sustaining the livelihoods provided to them. It measured the interconnectedness of livelihoods to the quality of life of marginalized sectors.

The implication drawn served as a basis for the development plan of future livelihood programs that dealt with improving the lives of marginalized in Calamba City. Thus, it was strongly believed that empowered and competent sectors could make a difference in uplifting their lives and their families' situations.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to assess the level of implementation of livelihood programs in Calamba City and how these programs related to the quality of life of marginalized sectors in improving their socio-economic growth. Specifically, it sought answers to the following:

1. Determine the level of implementation of different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors in terms of:

- 1.1 Applicability,
 - 1.2 Acceptability,
 - 1.3 Marketability, and
 - 1.4 Sustainability.
2. Determine the quality of life among marginalized sectors in terms of:
 - 2.1 Life satisfaction,
 - 2.2 Affluent life, and
 - 2.3 Rich life aspiration.
 3. Determine if there was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life among marginalized sectors in Calamba City.
 4. Describe the lived experience of the participants from the marginalized sectors on to the implementation of livelihood programs and their quality of life.
 5. Propose livelihood programs based on the findings of the study.
-

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized the mixed method, particularly the explanatory sequential approach. It was the most appropriate design because the study assessed the level of implementation of livelihood programs among marginalized sectors in terms of their applicability, sustainability, marketability, and acceptability, the quality of life in terms of their life satisfaction, affluent life, and rich life aspiration, significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and quality of life, lived experiences of respondents from marginalized sectors, and the livelihood programs that could be proposed.

Creswell (2018, as cited in Foley Library Gonzaga University, 2022) defined the explanatory sequential design as the two-design phase where the quantitative data was analyzed and collected first, then the qualitative data was analyzed based on the results of quantitative data. Qualitative data was also used to explain quantitative data.

Creswell and Plano (2018, as cited in Draucker et al., 2020) described the sequential explanatory design as one of the approaches of mixed method in which the qualitative data was used to enhance and follow up the unexpected quantitative findings. It was often narrating the data to interpret the numeric findings of unexpected events.

The research conducted by Othman et al. (2020) emphasized the use of mixed methods in guiding the actions of individuals and the reflection of the researcher's worldviews. It is referred to as the combination of the strength of both quantitative and qualitative data. In the quantitative phase, the collection of data through survey questionnaire was used for validity and reliability. Meanwhile, for qualitative, there were strategies applied to maintain the trustworthiness which included the in-depth interviews,

transcription and analysis of data, member checking, critical self-reflection, stability, accuracy, to name a few. The integration of data was essential for thorough understanding of phenomenon.

The focus of this approach was to interpret and explain the relationship between variables. The quantitative data were collected and analyzed, following the collection and analysis of qualitative data. The results were interpreted in ways that usually give weight and emphasis to the quantitative data. Separate phrases of design, data collection, and reporting for quantitative and qualitative data were considered strengths and the weaknesses were the time and resources needed for the collection of data separately.

Thus, the researcher applied this research design using quantitative data to assess the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the status of quality of life among marginalized sectors and qualitative data to analyze and interpret the findings of quantitative results.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Calamba City. This locale was considered because of the familiarity of the researcher who was an employee in the City Government of Calamba, specifically in the Gender and Development Office. The data gathered came from the identified marginalized sectors in the city who were the beneficiaries of livelihood programs. It was beneficial to conduct a study on how the marginalized sectors could access services and opportunities given by the government. The study was conducted during the school year 2023-2024.

Population and Sampling

In this study, purposive sampling was used for the quantitative data of the study and purposeful sampling for the qualitative data of the study. These were the most appropriate samplings as the researcher focused on the lives of marginalized sectors who were the beneficiaries of livelihood programs offered by the city government of Calamba.

According to Campbell (2020), purposive sampling better matched the aims and objectives of the research, thus improving the rigor of the study and the trustworthiness of data and results. It moved away from any random form of sampling and strategies to make sure specific kinds of cases would possibly be included in the final research of the study. It assumed that people hold different and important views about ideas, issues, and questions. Meanwhile, Ames et al. (2019) explained purposive sampling as a kind of sampling used for special situations to select cases with a specific purpose in mind.

Moreover, Nikolopoulou (2022) explained purposive sampling as a non-probability sampling technique that was selected 'on purpose' when identifying the individuals, cases, or events that can provide the best information in achieving the study's objectives. Also, it was common in qualitative research and mixed methods research as it was

particularly useful if needed to find information-rich cases or make the most out of limited resources.

The use of purposive sampling was important to the study because it enabled the researcher to describe the impact of findings thoroughly and gather responses to have more precise results. This sampling focused on specific areas of interest and an in-depth analysis of the characteristics of marginalized sectors.

Furthermore, Creswell (2018, as cited in Staller, 2020) illustrated the purposeful sampling as a selection of people and sites to clearly understand the phenomenon. It developed perspectives and understanding that could be useful in enlightening the cases or situations and describing and unfolding the participants and respondents of the study.

Meanwhile, the study of Palinkas et al. (2015, as cited in De Castro, 2021) explained the wide use of purposeful sampling in qualitative research to identify and select information-rich cases of the phenomenon using limited resources. It highlighted the knowledge and experience of participants to communicate, reflect, and express their opinions.

The study used purposeful sampling to determine the potential impact of livelihood programs on the lives of marginalized sectors. The purposeful sampling was appropriate because it provided recommendations and strategies to the city government of Calamba that could be used when implementing different programs suitable to the needs of marginalized sectors.

Respondents of the Study

For the Quantitative Data, the study utilized a total of 150 respondents as shown in Table A:

Table A

Respondents Profile

Type of Sector	Gender	Age Range	Total
Formal	Male	21-53 years old	18
	Female	19-61 years old	30
Informal	Male	21-57 years old	33
	Female	18-65 years old	69
Total Respondents			150

Of the 150 respondents, 18 males aged 21 to 53 years old and 30 females aged 19 to 61 years old came from the formal sector. Meanwhile, 33 males aged 21 to 57 years old and 69 females aged 18 to 65 years old came from the informal sector.

Participants of the Study

For the Qualitative Data, the researcher utilized 10 participants who received different livelihood programs as shown in Table B.

Of the ten (10) participants; two males aged 40 years old and 66 years old who worked as Farmer and Cooperative President were interviewed. The participants received vegetable seeds, fertilizers, and chicken from the city government. Meanwhile, eight females aged 53 years old, 34 years old, 43 years old, 57 years old, 59 years old, 46 years old, 57 years old, and 49 years old worked as Mushroom Grower/ Sectoral, Farmers, Businesswoman, Cooperative Presidents, Sewer/Mushroom Grower, Housewife, Fisherfolk, and Farmers were interviewed. The participants have received mushrooms, rabbits, pigs, vegetable seeds, rice, farming equipment, sewing machines, broiler production, fingerling, and feeds from the city government.

Table B

Participants Profile

Participants/ Type of sector	Age	Gender	Occupation	Type of livelihood program/s received
Participant Formal	1/ 53	Female	Mushroom Grower/ Sectoral	Mushroom Rabbit, Pig,
Participant Informal	2/ 34	Female	Farmer	Vegetable seeds
Participant Informal	3/ 43	Female	Businesswoman	Rice
Participant Informal	4/ 57	Female	Cooperative President	Pig, Farming Equipment, Vegetable seeds, Rabbit
Participant Informal	5/ 59	Female	Sewer/Mushroom Grower	Sewing machine, Mushroom
Participant Informal	6/ 46	Female	Housewife	Broiler production
Participant Informal	7/ 66	Male	Cooperative President	Vegetable seeds, fertilizer, chicken
Participant Informal	8/ 57	Female	Fisherfolk	Fingerling, feeds
Participant Informal	9/ 40	Male	Farmer	Vegetable seeds, fertilizer
Participant Informal	10/ 49	Female	Farmer	Broiler, fertilizer, vegetable seeds

The respondents and participants of this study have ages ranging from twenty-one (21), the youngest, to sixty-six (66), the oldest. There were ninety-nine females (99) and fifty-one (51) males. They have been categorized as marginalized working in formal and informal sectors.

Instrument

The instruments used were validated researcher-made surveys and semi-structured interview questionnaires to gather the data from the marginalized sectors. The questionnaire was drawn out based on the researcher’s previous readings of related studies and literature, published articles, and theses relevant to the study. The survey

describing the implication of the implementation of livelihood to the lives of respondents was openly constructed to accommodate the preparedness in answering the questionnaire.

The survey questionnaire had four dimensions. The first indicator was the level of implementation in terms of applicability, sustainability, marketability, and acceptability; the second was the quality of life of marginalized sectors in terms of life satisfaction, affluent life, and rich life aspiration; the third indicator was the significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and quality of life, and the fourth indicator was the proposed program based on the result of the study.

The questionnaires were evaluated using the four-point Likert scale of (4) Fully Implemented, (3) Implemented, (2) Partially Implemented, and (1) Not Implemented for the level of implementation and four-point Likert scale of (4) Very Satisfactory, (3) Satisfactory, (2) Fair, and (1) Poor for the quality of life of marginalized sectors.

The researcher also conducted interviews for an in-depth analysis of the study.

As for the semi-structured interview questions, these were:

1. What livelihood program/s of the government do you have access to and are suitable to your needs? Was the quality of life achievable through livelihood programs?
2. How are these livelihood programs implemented?
3. How do these livelihood programs provide opportunities to you and your family?
4. What livelihood strategies you have adopted that improve your lives?
5. How do the skills acquired empower you as an individual?
6. How do the government strategies help you in measuring relevance and timeliness of livelihood programs being implemented?
7. How do these livelihood programs increase your profit in the market?
8. How do these livelihood programs help yourself and your family?
9. What do you aspire/ wish to have in life?

Validation of the Instrument

The survey questionnaires were presented to the thesis adviser, quantitative data analyst/statistician, and panelists for comments and suggestions. Meanwhile, the interview guide questions were presented and validated by the thesis adviser and qualitative data analyst for a thorough understanding of the study. For the development and comprehensive study, some professionals were sought to validate the instrument. These professionals were composed of a research director, statistician, qualitative data analyst, and two (2) supervising administrative officers from the city government of Calamba who used to be implementers of livelihood programs.

Some items in the questionnaires were added and deleted based on the advice of the validators. Furthermore, the interview guide questions for qualitative data were validated by the qualitative data expert and the thesis adviser. Comments and suggestions were incorporated for the development of the study. Upon approval, the

survey questionnaires and interview guide questions were disseminated to marginalized sectors that have access to different livelihood programs in the city.

Meanwhile, the proportion of relevance of S-CVI Average had met the satisfactory level of 1.0. Thus, the scale of questionnaire had achieved the satisfactory level of content validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the data, the study applied the following procedures:

First, the list of marginalized sectors was generated in the Gender and Development Management Information System (GADMIS). Implementers were also coordinated to verify the respondents' accessibility to different livelihood programs funded by GAD.

Upon approval of the thesis adviser, the survey questionnaires were prepared to gain information about the marginalized sectors' access to different livelihood programs offered by the city government. The 150 respondents were distributed with printed copies of questionnaires. Results from survey questionnaires were tabulated, consolidated, and interpreted. Google form was also made to input the answers of respondents for easier computation of the result of the survey. Data was submitted to a statistician for interpretation of the result.

Furthermore, interviews were conducted with ten (10) participants to know their experiences on the programs implemented. Interview guide questions in verbatim form were produced for the participants' better understanding. Some interviews were performed through calls, face-to-face, and video calls in Messenger. Follow-up interviews were also conducted to gather and clarify the data provided by the participants. The results of the interviews were transcribed and submitted to the qualitative data analyst for interpretation of data.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

The following statistical treatment was applied using the Likert Scale, frequency, and mean to assess the level of implementation of livelihood programs and quality of life among marginalized sectors. The study used the purpose statements in the level of implementation of livelihood, quality of life among marginalized sectors, significant relationships of implemented livelihood programs and quality of life, and proposed livelihood program.

Moreover, the study conducted a pilot test on twenty (20) respondents and interpreted by an institutional statistician using Cronbach Alpha to measure and assess the reliability and internal consistency of questions. The Cronbach Alpha as explained by Abbadia (2023) evaluated the reliability of variables between many items that comprised an instrument to the quantity of the total variable. Reliability was produced when the same

collection of items would result in the same responses to identical questions when administered to the same respondents.

The Cronbach Alpha result was excellent with values of .978 for applicability, .966 for acceptability, .969 for marketability, and .977 for sustainability in the level of livelihood implementation. The quality of life had values of .975 for life satisfaction, .977 for affluent life, and .978 for rich life aspiration.

Treatment of Qualitative Data

The study interviewed ten (10) participants who agreed to share their experiences regarding the level of implementation of livelihood programs and their quality of life. The interview used Thematic Analysis which had taken the bodies of data (which were often quite large) and groups according to similarities. It was a set of interviews or focus group transcripts that could be useful for finding out about people's experiences, views, and opinions.

The study used thematic analysis of qualitative data in the form of a transcription of in-depth interviews with the marginalized sectors. Data were in audio files or recordings being transcribed in verbatim form. The transcripts were submitted to a qualitative data analyst for the application of codes. The Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) was used to focus on the lived experiences of individuals using collated data like interviews, analyzed and uncovered themes and their meanings, and helped the researcher understand individuals' experiences. It transformed into the charged experiences that often 'mark' or leave a lasting impact on people's lives. The study by Braun and Clarke (2006, as cited in Tarcilo, 2022), explained the IPA procedures that had undergone different systematic phases. Phase 1, referred to the familiarization of collected data; Phase 2, was about generating or combining different codes; Phase 3, searching for appropriate themes; Phase 4, was about reviewing themes; and Phase 5, was about clustering the defined themes. Various codes were combined and made into sub-themes. Some themes were removed, merged, and re-arranged to support the data. From the responses of marginalized sectors and formulation of sub-themes, the result of the study was analyzed, narrated with coherent stories based on the presented data, and supported with previous studies and literature related to the present study.

RESULTS

Purpose Statement 1. Determine the level of implementation of different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors in terms of:

1.1 Applicability

Table 1.1
Level of Implementation of Different Livelihood Programs Offered by the City Government of Calamba to Marginalized Sectors in terms of Applicability

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The implementation of livelihood programs ...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Are suitable to the needs of marginalized sectors	3.21	I	3.20	I	3.21	I
2. Provides sufficient technical and financial support for effective livelihood programs to marginalized sectors	3.21	I	3.21	I	3.21	I
3. Strengthens awareness and skills of marginalized sectors through appropriate training	3.15	I	3.19	I	3.17	I
4. Influences the decision-making of marginalized sectors in accessing the livelihood programs	3.13	I	3.16	I	3.15	I
5. Benefits predominantly the marginalized sectors who receive the livelihood programs	3.08	I	3.19	I	3.14	I
Standard Deviation					0.80	
General Assessment	3.15	I	3.19	I	3.17	I

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Fully Implemented (HI) 2.50 - 3.24 Implemented (I) 1.75 - 2.49 Partially Implemented (MI) 1.00 - 1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

1.2 Acceptability

Table 1.2
Level of Implementation of Different Livelihood Programs Offered by the City Government of Calamba to Marginalized Sectors in terms of Acceptability

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
The implementation of livelihood programs ...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Are compatible to the marginalized sectors' skills and knowledge	3.13	I	3.19	I	3.16	I
2. Improve opportunity for marginalized sectors through access to skills training on enterprise development	3.13	I	3.24	I	3.19	I
3. Enable the marginalized sectors to adapt different livelihood strategies	3.29	FI	3.20	I	3.25	FI
4. Empowers marginalized sectors to improve livelihood program through the new skills acquired	3.23	I	3.25	FI	3.24	I
5. Facilitate the active participation of marginalized sectors in livelihood strategies for development intervention	3.21	I	3.25	I	3.23	I
Standard Deviation					0.75	
General Assessment	3.20	I	3.22	I	3.21	I

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Fully Implemented (HI) 2.50 - 3.24 Implemented (I) 1.75 - 2.49 Partially Implemented (MI) 1.00 - 1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

1.3 Marketability

Table 1.3
Level of Implementation of Different Livelihood Programs Offered by the City Government of Calamba to Marginalized Sectors in terms of Marketability

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
The implementation of livelihood programs ...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Create platform for easy access to market and promotion of goods and services	3.21	I	3.11	I	3.16	I
2. Demonstrate citizen-centric marketing focusing the real needs of marginalized sectors	3.13	I	3.15	I	3.14	I
3. Observe aims that are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and timely (SMART) livelihood programs and strategies for marginalized sectors	3.04	I	3.16	I	3.10	I
4. Identify clearly the ideal target beneficiaries of the program and draws the marginalized sectors' attention to goods and services available	3.17	I	3.22	I	3.20	I
5. Determine the value of services provided and fulfills the marginalized sectors' needs or desires through profit, market opportunity, environmental, legal and performance expectations and standards	3.13	I	3.20	I	3.17	I
Standard Deviation					0.79	
General Assessment	3.13	I	3.16	I	3.15	I

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Fully Implemented (HI) 2.50 - 3.24 Implemented (I) 1.75 - 2.49 Partially Implemented (MI) 1.00 - 1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

1.4 Sustainability

Table 1.4
Level of Implementation of Different Livelihood Programs Offered by the City Government of Calamba to Marginalized Sectors in terms of Sustainability

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
The implementation of livelihood programs ...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Gain viable profits and provide for marginalized sectors' family in the long run	3.21	I	3.19	I	3.20	I
2. Generate employment or income among marginalized sectors into sustainable livelihoods towards economic stability	3.17	I	3.23	I	3.20	I
3. Create enabling environment through establishment and strengthening of networks of implementing social safety net services, providers of working capital, and participants from marginalized sectors	3.21	I	3.17	I	3.19	I
4. Raise living standards and alleviate poverty of marginalized sectors	3.15	I	3.14	I	3.15	I
5. Enable a continuous improvement of the marginalized sectors' quality of life	3.10	I	3.18	I	3.14	I

Standard Deviation					0.79
General Assessment	3.17	I	3.18	I	3.18 I

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Fully Implemented (HI) 2.50 - 3.24 Implemented (I) 1.75 - 2.49 Partially Implemented (MI) 1.00 - 1.74 Not Implemented (NI)

Purpose Statement 2. Determine the quality of life among marginalized sectors in terms of:

2.1 Life Satisfaction

Table 2.1
Level of Quality of Life among Marginalized Sectors in terms of Life Satisfaction

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Manifest satisfaction in preparing daily activities	3.23	S	3.14	S	3.19	S
2. Give themselves the feeling of self-respect and self-worth in every endeavor	3.19	S	3.17	S	3.18	S
3. Ensure good sleep, capacity for work, and personal relationships	3.27	VS	3.22	S	3.25	VS
4. Meet enough relaxation and leisure with positive psychological outlook and emotional well-being	3.17	S	3.21	S	3.19	S
5. Demonstrate good physical and mental health ability to do the things he/she wants to do	3.23	S	3.22	S	3.23	S
Standard Deviation					0.73	
General Assessment	3.22	S	3.19	S	3.21	S

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory (VS) 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory (S) 1.75 - 2.49 Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Poor (P)

2.2 Affluent Life

Table 2.2
Level of Quality of Life among Marginalized Sectors in terms of Affluent Life

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Meet life stability, comfort, enjoyment, and pleasantness	3.19	S	3.25	VS	3.22	S
2. Experience financial freedom, excellent health care services, good facilities, infrastructure, and school	3.21	S	3.20	S	3.21	S
3. Participate in social activities or gatherings and recreation	3.13	S	3.12	S	3.13	S
4. Live in a successful career and acquire luxuries goods	3.10	S	3.07	S	3.09	S
5. Donate to charity or does volunteer works	3.10	S	2.95	S	3.03	S
Standard Deviation					0.81	
General Assessment	3.15	S	3.12	S	3.14	S

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory (VS) 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory (S) 1.75 - 2.49 Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Poor (P)

2.3 Rich Life Aspiration

Table 2.3
Level of Quality of Life among Marginalized Sectors in terms of Rich Life Aspiration

Indicators	Employees		Customers		Composite	
...	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
1. Seek for novel experiences like travel, literature, film, music, sports, and arts	3.13	S	3.05	S	3.09	S
2. Plan for unusual and perspective-changing experiences, such as living abroad for an extended period of time	3.10	S	3.02	S	3.06	S
3. Pay off debt and starts prioritizing saving goals and investment	3.17	S	3.22	S	3.20	S
4. Desire a meaningful life by living in a stable economic and political conditions of stability and happy life	3.27	VS	3.36	VS	3.32	VS
5. Pursue money or power by creating multiple streams of incomes	3.40	VS	3.30	VS	3.35	VS
Standard Deviation						0.78
General Assessment	3.21	S	3.19	S	3.20	S

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Very Satisfactory (VS) 2.50 - 3.24 Satisfactory (S) 1.75 - 2.49 Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Poor (P)

Purpose Statement 3. Determine if there was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life among marginalized sectors in Calamba City.

Table 3
Test of Significant Relationship between Level of Implementation of Livelihood Programs and Level of Quality of Life among Marginalized Sectors in Calamba City

Level of Implementation	Quality of Life	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Applicability	Life Satisfaction	.758**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Affluent Life	.735**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Rich Life Aspiration	.727**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Acceptability	Life Satisfaction	.707**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Affluent Life	.691**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Rich Life Aspiration	.696**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Marketability	Life Satisfaction	.721**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Affluent Life	.699**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Rich Life Aspiration	.742**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Sustainability	Life Satisfaction	.704**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Affluent Life	.672**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Rich Life Aspiration	.748**	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Purpose Statement 4. Describe the lived experiences of the participants from the marginalized sectors on to the implementation of livelihood programs and their quality of life.

Interview Question 1: What livelihood program/s of the government do you have access to and are suitable to your needs?

THEME A: Farming, Poultry, and Fishing Government Initiated Programs		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 1	Pero ang pinaka ano po namin ngayon ay yung sa mushroom.	Mushroom Cultivation
Participant 2	Unang natanggap namin ay sisiw...kaya nga lang di sya nagsuccess gawa ng panahon. Ang pangalawa ay ang mushroom...ahm...tinanggap namin to galing sa gobyerno.	
Participant 3	... buto.	Farm Fertilizers and Farm Seeds
Participant 4	... seeds, fertilizer.	
Participant 5	... abono, mga buto po.	
Participant 6	... buto, fertilizer at gamot.	
Participant 7	For example, pecking duck, mga ganyan...and then yung mga chicken na palahiin, so yun. Kasama yun...part yun ng naattendan naming seminar and then nareceive namin yung broiler management...yung sisiw nga.	Chicken and Duck Poultry
Participant 8	Pati na rin training sa pag-aalaga ng mga hayupan... mga manok na paitlogin..	
Participant 9	Ang naibigay po saamin ay fingerling sa hito na may kasamang feeds. Sa asawa ko po yun. Katulad yan yung mga maghihito nabigyan ng fingerling. Identified ng government kung sino maghihito.	Fish Farming
Participant 10	Rice subsidy.	Rice Subsidy

Interview Question 2: How are these livelihood programs implemented?

THEME B: Government Initiatives		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 1	At pinalalaganap na po namin ito sa bawat barangay at tinatie-up na din po ito sa bawat school. Bale po sa ngayon isa din po ako sa nag ano ng..inaayos na po namin para sa Division ng DepEd	Local Government Initiatives
Participant 2	una yan inaanyayahan ka ng government...kung ikaw ay willing umattend ng seminars.	

Participant 10	Bale ang nangyari...syempre may proseso yan, interview muna kung talagang ako ay karapat-dapat. Kasi meron mga taong walang kakayahan...kailangan talagang i-evaluate. So since nakita talaga na kailangan naman talaga ng mga kabuhayan dahil meron akong tatlong anak na nag-aaral at walang may hanapbuhay sa aming pamilya, ako ang naging kuwalipikado. Yun ang pinagpasimulan ko para ako magkaroon ng hanapbuhay.	
Participant 4	Nakikipagpartner si CLDD. Meron syang project kagaya ng rabbit production...so partnership with Department of Agriculture and CLDO with Sir Philip. So, pag nagseminar ka, meron kang trio...so ang nagbabayad doon ay CLDO tapos binibigay doon sa mga sineminar.	
Participant 8	Pag ibinigay ang intervention, livelihood program ng LGU o di kaya ay national government Department of Agriculture, ipinamamahagi naman namin sa mga miyembro.	
Participant 9	Katulad yan yung mga maghihito nabigyan ng fingerling. Identified ng government kung sino maghihito.	
Participant 5	Nilalakad po ng pinaka President po sa Cityhall bago pinamamahagi po sa mga Samahan dito.	
Participant 3	Kasi nga po cooperative at eco-farm...tas sa farm po.	Thru Livelihood Cooperative and Association
Participant 6	Ano naman kasi kami association.	
Participant 7	Pinatutupad nila ito sa pamamagitan ng...yun nga pagcommunicate sa iba't-ibang uri ng mga kababaihan, for example. And then through seminars din. Pag nakaattend ka po ng seminar regarding po dito. Yun yung nagstart ang implementation nila.	Thru Livelihood Seminars

Question 3: How do these livelihood programs provide opportunities to you and your family?

THEME C: Income and Agricultural Materials		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 1	Nagkaroon po ako ng extra income..	Extra Source of Income
Participant 10	Kasi yung livelihood program na ipinagkaloob sa akin, that time lahat ng anak ko nag-aaral...so kailangan ko umisip kung saan ako kukuha ng pangaraw-araw naming pagkain, pambaon nila araw-araw. Alam ko na...na meron na akong pagkukuhanan. Nasa goal mo yan kung gusto mom aging maunlad ang Negosyo mo syempre pagbutihin para yung kita mo...yung pangangailangan ng pamilya mo, matustusan mo.	
Participant 4	Pag binigyan mo sila ng livelihood, meron silang pagkakakitaan. Meron silang back-up.	
Participant 2	Ibibigay nila sayo, ang gagawin mo nalang pangalagaan mo sya at paunlarin mo kung ano ang ibinigay sayo.	
Participant 7	Syempre mag-aalaga ka ng sisiw...may costing, and then diba makakapagbenta ka. Yun yung kapakinabangan eh. Dun mo makikita ang kapakinabangan dahil dun kikita ka doon sa uri ng livelihood.	

Participant 8	Nakakatulong yan ng malaki. Unang-una nagkakanegosyo ka ng walang puhunan. Minsan nga ang bigay ng LGU meron pang kuwan...may initial na patuka pa pag sa manok, sa baboy gayon din.	
Participant 9	Malaking tulong yun samin dahil binigyan kami ng paunang yan para palaguin namin. Dyan po kami magsimula. Kung meron naman po kami ng dati, dagdag sa kabuhayan po.	
Participant 6	Nakakatulong sya samin kasi pang extrang income saming mga farmers.	
Participant 3	Sa kooperatiba po. Kapag po kasi kami binigyan ng seeds, nagbibigay din po kami sa mga members na farmers. Diba po nagfafarming po kami...may sarili po kaming farm. Ginagamit po namin ang seeds pag itanim po namin. Pinagbibili po namin tas sa family na po namin kasi yung seeds po na binigay sa kooperatiba tas binigyan po ng kooperatiba ang member nya na farmer, bigay na po yun ng kooperatiba. Kasi di naman po lahat magagamit kaya sinishare din po sa members.	Aide for Farmers
Participant 5	Okay naman po kasi...laking tulong na po yun kasi hindi na kami bibili tulad ng mga abono tsaka po mga buto. Kumbaga laking tulong na po yun kasi po sa taas po ng abono tsaka po mga buto. Mahal po kasi.	

Question 4: What livelihood strategies have you adopted that improve your lives?

THEME D: Assistance, Expansion, and Adjustment Strategies		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 8	Katulad sa agrikultura...sa agrikultura kasi may mga trainings ang pagtanim. Although marunong na naman sila na magtanim, ay yun ay sinusupplement pa ng mga pag-aaral at trainings na binibigay samin ng LGU tsaka national government.	Assistance Strategy thru training and seminars
Participant 9	Halimbawa po pag may seminar na ibinigay, kung mapasama man po sila sa seminar sila po ang umaattend kasi sila nag-aalaga sa hito. Kami naman meron din naman kaming baklad. Syempre pag po ba...pag may alam ka sa pag aalaga mas maganda po diba ma'am...mapapaunlad nyo pa yung pag-aalga, mapaparami. At syempre kung alam namin ang pag-aalaga halimbawa magkasakit ang mga hito paano gagawin. Syempre pagka may seminar, alam mo ang gagawain. Hindi ka matatakot na malugi ka.	
Participant 6	Malaking naitutulong sakin ang mga trainings.	
Participant 2	Pero napakalaking tulong kasi yun nga bawat bigay ng government pangalagaan mo kung anong meron ka para nagagamit mo habang nabubuhay ka. Yung mga strategies na natutunan ko dyan, dapat may pasensya ka, diba. Bawat ginagawa mo kailangan may pasensya ka. Sa pasensya mo dun ka magbubunga...kasi dun mo makikita yung pinagpasensyahan mo na ginagawa mo. Kasi kung wala kang pasensya at naiinis ka na...ano ba yan ayaw magbunga...ano ba yan nabulok, ganun natutunan ko...dapat may pasensya ka sa lahat ng ginagawa mo. At tsaka dapat masaya ka sa ginagawa mo.	Adjustment Strategy thru Hard work and Perseverance

Participant 7	Unang-una, kailangan ng sipag at pagtatyaga...yun yung unang-una na mai-aim mo sa...na para sa sarili mo. Kasi lahat naman ng bagay mahirap gawin so kailangan talaga ng dobleng sipag, dobleng pagtatyaga doon sa uri ng livelihood na gaganapin mo.	
Participant 10	...kapag pala ikaw may pangkabuhayan matututo kang makisama, magmanage...maliit man o malaki na business, matututo kang magmanage ng negosyo para maging maunlad, para mamonitor mo kung kumikita ka o hindi. Kung kailangan mo ba ng plan B mo para hindi mawala ang hanapbuhay na ipinagkaloob sayo. Para patuloy ang kita mo.	Expansion Strategy thru income creation, networking, and marketing
Participant 4	Next yung marketing naman. And hopefully magkaroon kami dito ng establishments, yung maluwang namin na lugar na yan is...paupahan namin sa mga gustong magtayo ng mga kainan.	
Participant 3	May napunta po dito nag-oonline po...kumukuha po sila dito. Nagpapaorder po sila...	
Participant 1	..nagkaroon po kami ng extra income na makakatulong din po doon sa pagbabayad ng bills kasi po bawat gumagawa kami at nagti-train, kahit papaano may binibigay po silang honorarium at isa na rin po ako sa nagmamarket. Kahit papaano may percentage po kami.	
Participant 5	Bale po yung mga binubunga po ng amin pong tinatanim na galing po sa amin, ako na po ang nagtitinda. Ako na po yung nagdadala sa Tanauan, sa kalakalan po. Laking tulong na rin po sa amin yung kinikita as in directa na po saamin.	

Question 5: How do the skills acquired empower you as an individual?

THEME E: By Gaining Additional Knowledge and Skills		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 6	Malaking naitutulong sakín ang mga trainings.	Knowledgeable and Skilled thru Livelihood Training and Seminar
Participant 10	...dapat maging matalino ka rin para ang Negosyo mo hindi mawala. Natuto akong magkilatis ng tao pati yung pagiging business-minded ako. Naging business-minded ako na naging resourceful pala ako, kahit maliit man, talagang naging resourceful ako. At tsaka although kahit sa maliit na puhunan, nasa sayon a din talaga ang pagpapalago...basta meron kanang pinagpasimulan na at kaya mong imanage, doon ka matututo eh kung gusto mo na hindi mawala.	
Participant 7	So, yung livelihood nakatulong para sakín kasi...ah...nagawa ko kasi yun base sa mga natutunan ko, base dun sa mga...mga yun nga learnings dun sa mga tinatawag natin...kasi ginawa mo, ginanap mo sya sa buhay mo. Inadopt mo eh. So, syempre, malaki ang natutunan ko, unang-una na syempre sap ag-aalaga nito...pag aalaga at pagmamanage.	
Participant 8	Sa pamamagitan ng pagsasanay, nadadagdagan ang aming kaalaman. Noong una konti lang ang kaalaman namin sap ag-aalaga ng baboy tsaka manok...ngayon alam na alam na namin. At sa pagtatanim man, ganun din naman.	

Participant 5	Malaking tulong po talaga. Kasi po yung inaapply po sa amin ng government na ibinabahagi nila...na...naibabahagi naman po sa pagtanim.	Breakthrough of the Mushroom Farming
Participant 4	So, nabibigyan namin sila ng assurance na may credibility kami at hindi lang kami basta nakiki-agri lang kasi equip kami with knowledge, equip kami with certification, legality. Natrain ako para maging equip sa field na to at para makapagturo sa iba. Sinishare ko ang alam ko.	
Participant 2	Kasi pag hindi ka interesado, hindi mo magagawa. Yung skills ah...ah...nasa sarili mo rin yan. Kapag interesado ka, umattend ka ng seminar, magagawa mo lahat yun.	
Participant 9	Paraan ng pag-aalaga po ng mga hito. Kaya yun po ang lagi naming hinihingi na dumami pa ang mga seminar na aattendan kung paano po namin matututunan ang ganoong paraan at para lalong gumanda ang pag-aalaga.	
Participant 3	Natututo po magbenta, paano magtanim, itanim.	
Participant 1	Inumpisahan po namin sa aming barangay dito sa Canlubang. At unti-unti din namin po itong pinapakilala sa iba't-ibang barangay na ngayon. Kaya po ngayon sa buong Calamba ay nakikilala na rin po ang mushroom...at syempre po una po doon, pag pinag-uusapan ang mushroom lalo na sa akin, una agad nila akong pinipin-point na dito po kasi...sa ngayon po gumagawa na po kami...nagbubuo po kami ng Calamba mushroom growers ng Calamba.	

Question 6: How do the government strategies help you in measuring relevance and timeliness of livelihood programs being implemented?

THEME F: Availability, Reliability, and Technical Efficiency		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 3	Natututo na, diba bawat seeds may iba't-ibang klase. May iba't ibang buwan kung kelan puwedeng itanim. Napag-aaralan, natututunan. Diba pag tag-ulan, may halaman na tag-ulan...	Applying the Acquired Knowledge and Skills thru Availability of Training and Seminars
Participant 4	Nagkakaroon ka ng bagong idea, kabuhayan...nagkakameron ka ng perseverance na mag-isip pa ng mga pupuwede mong gawin. Pero pagdating sa idea, nagkakaroon kami ng bagong ideya.	
Participant 7	So ngayon, para sa akin malaking tulong yung kanilang strategy na naiisip na yan kasi yung mga kagaya namin na individual natututo at the same time nakikinabang. Kumbaga yung mga programa ng gobyerno ay naibababa nila sa bawat indibidwal dito sa mga Calambeno. Masasabi kong maganda yung strategy na naisip nila na yung mga ganitong uri ng livelihood ay nare-reach out nila lalo na yung mga tao na nasa mga laylayan.	
Participant 8	Unang-una tinatanong nila kung sino ba ang mga interesado...mga prospective na magiging participant. Syempre yung mga participant ay interesado, may pagmamalasakit sa pagsasaka at livelihood. Kasi buhay na nila yan eh. At kapag nalaman ng gobyerno natin magse-set sila ng training, magcoconduct at ibibgay naman nila saamin.	

Participant 5	Inaapply namin po kung paano at kelan aanihin yung gulay.	Technical Efficiency to Business Opportunities
Participant 10	Kumbaga yung isip ko na-open, nabukasan sa ganyang larangan na ang pagbubusiness, maliit man o malaki, talagang ano ka, kailangan mong maging ano sa Negosyo...matalino para hindi mawala yung binigay sayo.	
Participant 6	Tuloy-tuloy naman ang kita nila.	Reliability to Government Support and Initiative
Participant 2	Nakatulong itong binibigay ng government, unang-una kasi biyuda ako. Syempre kapag biyuda ka, ang hanap mo, hanapbuhay talaga. Mapagkakakitaan para maitaguyod ang mga anak mo lalong-lalo na nung ang mga anak ko ay nagco-college. Malaking tulong sya kasi pandagdag kahit pamasaha. Kahit na walang meryenda basta may pamasaha sila. Yun ang malaking tulong na naibigay saakin.	
Participant 9	Malaking tulong po sa amin dahil nabigyan kami ng pagkakataon na mabigyan kami ng libreng fingerlings na para din saaming kabuhayan para sa aming mga anak. Kaya dapat lang po talaga, nagbigay ang gobyerno dapat pangalagaan tlaga. ...	
Participant 1	Ma'am, bale ang sa government namin ngayon very supportive lalo na po yung DA. Pag nagti-training po sila under ng sa mga gardening...bale sinasama po nila ang mushroom. At ang government ay nagsusupply naman po sila ng pangangailangan, kumbaga starter kit sa mga taong nag-aral ng training. At least meron po silang maumpisahan para po sa pangkabuhayan nila.	

Question 7: How do these livelihood programs increase your profit in the market?

THEME G: Marketing and Financial Strategies		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 4	Online marketing. Meron kami through ATI naman. So, tinuruan naman kami ng digital marketing pero syempre hindi naman ganun kalaki yung...more on kasi ito ng eco-farm. Eco-tourism farm. So, ang amin is a little of everything. Yung ano namin dito ay hindi talaga yung maximize farming o commercial farming.	Online Marketing
Participant 3	Sa pamamagitan ng harvest time, benebenta at ang iba pa pong mga kasamahan ay benebenta online.	
Participant 2	Yung mga pangkabuhayan para makatulong sa sarili mo na mapataas yun, kailangan sipag at tiyaga. Pag wala kang sipag at tiyaga, hindi mo mapapataas ang iyong antas ng pangkabuhayan. Kahit anong laki ng puhunan, kapag ikaw ay tamad, wala diba.	
Participant 9	Ngayon, maganda ang benta mo, yun ay para sa pamilya mo na tapos madadagdagan halimbawa ang binigay sayo ay limang libo o tatlong libong similya, pag napaganda mo o napalaki mo ng ayos yun...nakaani ka ng maganda, sa susunod na aalagaan o, madadagdagan nay un.	Profit Gain
Participant 7	Karagdagan lang kasi yang kita...So malaking bagay kasi additional sya. For example ito nga pong pag-aalaga ng sisiw, syempre may karagdagang kita dito eh...	

Participant 10	May notebook kasi ako na sulatan, syempre may presyo yun na may tubo na tayo...hindi man mahal pero kikita tayo kasi pag sobrang mahal hindi tatangkilikin ng tao. Kung ang tubo mo naman ay hindi kalakihan pero mauubos din agad edi maganda ang pasok ng income sayo. Konti man pero mabilis ang benta.	
Participant 8	Talagang nakakatulong yan neng. Noon walang intervention katulad ng pagbibigay ng abono, mga trainings. Siguro meron mga livelihood noon pero very minimal lang. Hindi katulad ngayon na parang full blast na sya at lahat ng barangay ay nabibigyan.	Intensified Implementation of Livelihood Trainings
Participant 6	Dagdag pang kaalaman.	
Participant 1	Sa ngayon po, maganda naman ang naging impact. Isa na rin po ito sa nagiging...first na pangkabuhayan dito sa Calamba-ang mushroom.	Unique Products
Participant 5	Sa merkado po hindi po yun katulad ng idadaan pa sa iba. Kaya yung price po nya nami-maintain po namin. Kaya malaking tulong po yung direkta na naidadala.	Product Pricing

Question 8: How do these livelihood programs help yourself and your family?

THEME H: Personal and Financial Development		
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES
Participant 3	Karagdagan lang kasi yang kita...So malaking bagay kasi additional sya. For example ito nga pong pag-aalaga ng sisiw, syempre may karagdagang kita dito eh...	Financial Aid for Education Expenses
Participant 10	Maliit man ang kinikita pero andun pa din ang puhunan ko...dun palang din alam kong may kikitain ako. Araw-araw na panggastos ng mga anak ko. Di naman puwedeng ang bata papasok sa school...Yun yung priority ko, at least kahit papaano ang baon nila doon na.	
Participant 2	Yung pinakatubo ang gawin mo wag mong kunin lahat, magtira ka rin para sa kapital para umunlad ng umunlad yung binigay sayo ng government na pangkabuhayan.. maipagmamalaki ko kahit ako ay biyuda, nakapagtapos ang lima kong anak ng kanilang piniling kurso.	
Participant 9	Siguro po yung maitawid namin yung pang araw-araw namin at mapag-aral ko ang mga anak ko gamit ang pangkabuhayan na naibigay samin.	
Participant 7	So ngayon ang masasabi ko lang dun na ang tagumpay eh yun nga nagkaroon ako ng additional income sa pamamagitan nito	
Participant 8	Unang-una, pag nakita kami nakita din ang miyembro. Nagkakaroon kami ng mga dibidendo.	Financial Gain
Participant 5	Sa loob po ng isang araw nakakapag-ipon...nakakapagtabi pa naman kahit papapano ng kaunting kita. Bukod po sa panggastos sa pang araw-araw Ay yung ito naman, nakakapag-ipon kami na naidadagdag namin...tulad ng nakapagpagawa po kami ng bahay. Tulong na rin po kaming mag-asawa bukod po sa kinikita sa gulay at sa pagtitinda, yun nakakaipon kami. Unti-unti namin napapagawa itong bahay.	
Participant 6	Naging maayos naman ang aming buhay.	

Participant 4	Kaya yung kita ko sa pagtanim, isisave ko yun para yung expenses sa bahay at sa farm. Yung...yung income na yun nagagamit nila para sa mga pangangailangan sa bahay nila at sa farm. nakakatulong para mapaunlad ang kanilang pamumuhay pagdating sa farming	Improvement of Life
Participant 1	Noong una po dahil isa lang akong plain housewife, hindi po ako nakikisalamuha. Dahil po sa mga programa, nakishare po ako sa mga livelihood programs, unti-unti ko po nadevelop ang sarili ko	Personal Growth and Development

Question 9: What do you aspire/ wish to have in life?

THEME I: Sustainability of Livelihood Program and Children's Education			
PARTICIPANT	RESPONSES	SUBTHEMES	
Participant 1	Unang-una ma'am syempre, hindi ko naman masasabi na habang panahon nandito ako. Ang inaano ko lang ma'am, lahat ng naturuan ko sana maging successful din sila at marating din po nila kung ano man ang narating ko ngayon. At sana naman po, ipapasa din po nila sa susunod na henerasyon at maging pakinabang din po sa susunod na kabataan.	To Pass on and Continue the Livelihood Programs to Future Generations	
Participant 4	Yung matrain ang mga katulad nyo na kabataan, ma-equip kayo sa knowledge...iba kasi utak ng kabataan, para sila na magtutuloy. At mamotivate din kayo na hindi puwedeng mawala ang farmers.		
Participant 2	Alam mo ang pinapangarap ko...sana ang tao matuto kung ano ang binigay ng gobyerno sayo. Sana yung mga taong binigyan ng livelihood, paunlarin nila, mahal in nila...kung ano ang binigay sa kanila ng government. Kasi minsan lang yan sa buhay eh. Hindi ka puwedeng umulit. Wag mong sayangin ang bawat biyayang ibinigay sayo ng government.		
Participant 8	Dapat kahit hindi yung matatanda ngayon...dapat mamulat ang mga kabataan sa livelihood program na sinasabi. At sana magtuloy-tuloy na yang livelihood program na yan. Hindi naman masama yan, bagkus nakakabuti sa isang tao, isang pamilya na magkaroon ng livelihood activities.		
Participant 3	Sana kahit ganito ang kabuhayan namin...sana makatapos ng pag-aaral ang aking mga anak.		Wishing for their Children to Finish Studies
Participant 10	Sana magkaroon pa ako ng extension kahit magkaroon sa ibang purok naman. Pag ako pinagkalooban ulit ng livelihood, magkakaroon ako ng expansion sa iba pang barangay.		
Participant 7	Wala ako masyadong winiwish. Ang gusto ko lang talaga makatapos ng pag-aaral ang mga anak ko. Yun lang.		
Participant 9	Sana tuloy tuloy itong ibinigay saamin na livelihood. Tsaka po sana yung mga anak ko mapagtapos ko kahit ito lang po ang hanapbuhay namin.		
Participant 5	Yung matapos ko tong bahay ko. Sana, kumita kami ng maganda talaga...as in talaga. Para maipatuloy na namin pagpapagawa nitong bahay. Kasi pagkumita ng maayos, makakapag-apon.		
Participant 6	Simpleng buhay lang tsaka makatapos ang mga anak ko ng sa ganun may maganda silang kinabukasan.		

DISCUSSION

Purpose Statement 1. Determine the level of implementation of different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors in terms of:

Applicability was **Implemented** (3.17, σ - .80) in the different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors. The indicator “Are suitable to the needs of marginalized sectors and provides sufficient technical and financial support for effective livelihood programs” had the highest composite mean of **3.21** interpreted as **Implemented**. On the other hand, the indicator “Benefits predominantly the marginalized sectors who receive the livelihood programs” yielded the lowest composite mean of 3.14 and interpreted as **Implemented**.

This implies that marginalized sectors are mostly concerned with how the suitability, and sufficient technical, and financial support influence the effectiveness of livelihood programs. All indicators that involved appropriate support for the needs of marginalized sectors affect the implementation of the government’s livelihood programs, thus, supporting them to establish and build relationships that can reach those who have been excluded. However, disengaging them when it comes to access to livelihood programs will fail the government’s efforts to tailor their real needs.

Acceptability was **Implemented** (3.21, σ -0.75) in different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors. The indicator “Enable the marginalized sectors to adapt different livelihood strategies” had the highest composite mean of **3.25** interpreted as **Fully Implemented**. On the other hand, the indicator “Are compatible to the marginalized sectors’ skills and knowledge” yielded the lowest composite mean of 3.16 interpreted as **Implemented**.

This implies marginalized sectors’ abilities to adapt to different strategies provide a basis for formulating policy recommendations that would be responsive to their needs effectively. However, their skills and knowledge of programs greatly influence allowing them to stand on their own and become financially stable.

Marketability was **Implemented** (3.15, σ - 0.79) in different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors. The indicator “Identify clearly the ideal target beneficiaries of the program and draws the marginalized sectors’ attention to goods and services available” had the highest composite mean of **3.20** interpreted as **Implemented**. On the other hand, the indicator “Observe aims that are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and timely (SMART) livelihood programs and strategies for marginalized sectors” yielded the lowest composite assessment of **3.10** interpreted as **Implemented**.

This implies that the goods and services available draw the marginalized sectors’ attention. Identifying clearly who are the target beneficiaries of livelihood programs and

drawing the goods and services available for them help in ensuring relevance to improve marginalized sectors' livelihoods. And for some instances, though programs are formulated, and the beneficiaries are identified, the SMART goals of progress and ideas are not easy to reach and/or achieve.

Sustainability was **Implemented** (3.18, σ -0.79) in the different livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba to marginalized sectors. The indicator "Gain viable profits and provide for marginalized sectors' family in the long run and Generate employment or income among marginalized sectors into sustainable livelihoods towards economic stability" had the highest composite mean of **3.20** interpreted as **Implemented**. On the other hand, the indicator "Enable a continuous improvement of the marginalized sectors' quality of life" yielded the lowest composite mean of **3.10** interpreted as **Implemented**.

This implies that marginalized sectors are mostly concerned with the profits, employment, and income provide economic stability for the marginalized sectors in the long run. These factors allowed the marginalized sectors to sustain their needs continuously; but did not compromise the happiness and comfort they experienced.

Purpose Statement 2. Determine the quality of life among marginalized sectors in terms of:

Life Satisfaction was **Satisfactory** (3.21, σ - 0.73) among marginalized sectors. The indicator "Ensure good sleep, capacity for work, and personal relationships" had the highest composite mean of 3.25 interpreted as Very Satisfactory. On the other hand, the indicator "Give themselves the feeling of self-respect and self-worth in every endeavor" yielded the lowest composite mean of 3.18 interpreted as Satisfactory.

It implies that marginalized sectors are mostly concerned with their good sleep, capacity for work, and personal relationships. These indicators greatly influence the performances of marginalized sectors; thus, self-respect and self-worth help them work through challenges, build resilience, and maintain their emotional health.

Affluent Life was **Satisfactory** (3.14, σ -0.81) among marginalized sectors. The indicator "Meet life stability, comfort, enjoyment, and pleasantness" had the highest composite assessment of 3.22 and interpreted as Satisfactory. On the other hand, the indicator "Donate to charity or does volunteer works" yielded the lowest composite assessment of 3.03 interpreted as Satisfactory.

It implies that marginalized sectors are mostly concerned with meeting their stability in life, comfort, enjoyment, and pleasantness. The marginalized sectors perceived a life that is comfortable and stable; however, as charity or volunteering continues it is often criticized to be dependent as the jobless poor continue to be poor, and the disparity between the rich and the poor increases gradually.

Rich Life Aspiration was **Satisfactory** (3.20, σ -0.78) among marginalized sectors. The indicator “Pursue money or power by creating multiple streams of incomes” had the highest composite mean of 3.35 and interpreted as Very Satisfactory. On the other hand, the indicator “Plan for unusual and perspective-changing experiences, such as living abroad for an extended period of time” yielded the lowest composite mean of 3.06 interpreted as Satisfactory.

It implies that marginalized sectors are mostly concerned with pursuing money or power by creating multiple streams of income. In a fast-paced environment, many people created different sources of income to satisfy their needs.

Purpose Statement 3. Determine if there was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life among marginalized sectors in Calamba City.

There was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life among marginalized sectors in Calamba City. All the probability values (0.000) were less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. Since the r- value generated were from .672 to .758, it showed that the strength of connection was moderate to very high positive correlation.

This indicates that there is a substantial link between the implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life. This means that the better the implementation of the livelihood programs, the better the quality of life. The result of the study emphasizes the interconnectedness of livelihood to the lives among marginalized sectors as it is subjected to improving their well-being and stability, creating growth in their social and economic statuses, empowering them as individuals, and enhancing their skills and abilities to sustain their livelihoods.

Purpose Statement 4. Describe the lived experiences of the participants from the marginalized sectors on to the implementation of livelihood programs and their quality of life.

Interview Question 1: What livelihood program/s of the government do you have access to and are suitable to your needs?

Theme A

Farming, Poultry, and Fishing Government Initiated Programs

With the theme, Farming, Poultry, and Fishing Government Initiated Programs, the marginalized participants expressed their experiences to various livelihood programs implemented by the government. These livelihoods came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

The implementation of the livelihood program created access and opportunities to the marginalized sectors. The **Chicken and Duck Poultry**, specifically mentioned by Participant 7, *“For example, pecking duck, mga ganyan...and then yung mga chicken na*

palahiin, so yun. Kasama yun...part yun ng naattendan naming seminar and then nareceive namin yung broiler management...yung sisiw nga.” was one of livelihood program provided to marginalized sectors. As part of empowerment and poverty alleviation, the government continuously distributes poultry livelihood to provide household income and ensure food stability to marginalized sectors.

However, for some beneficiaries, the broiler livelihood didn't succeed because of the weather. This led them to shift to **Mushroom Cultivation** as what Participant 2 emphasized, *“Unang natanggap namin ay sisiw...kaya nga lang di sya nagsuccess gawa ng panahon. Ang pangalawa ay ang mushroom...ahm...tinanggap namin to galing sa gobyerno.”* in an interview. Even landless marginalized sectors could benefit from mushroom cultivation since it has an environment-friendly way of farming. The mushroom production would provide chances to employment and encourage the development of new products.

Meanwhile, **the Fish Farming** was provided to marginalized fisherfolks as what Participant 9 stated, *“Ang naibigay po saamin ay fingerling sa hito na may kasamang feeds. Sa asawa ko po yun. Katulad yan yung mga maghihito nabigyan ng fingerling. Identified ng government kung sino maghihito.”* as part of livelihood opportunities to their families. Creating development in employment, the small-scale fisheries and aquaculture activities were essential in provided food to many people and improving the local economy in coastal communities.

Implementation of livelihood programs caters to the needs of marginalized sectors who engage in farming and aquaculture activities. Since these activities occupied a larger portion of the economic growth and survival of individuals, creating programs suitable to their needs would improve their abilities and uplift their way of living.

Interview Question 2: How are these livelihood programs implemented?

Theme B

Government Initiatives

With the theme, Government Initiatives, the marginalized participants provided their experiences of the selection process they had undergone to be qualified to the livelihood programs. These livelihoods initiatives came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

Through **Local Government Initiatives**, selection process was conducted to determine if the marginalized sectors were qualified to the implemented livelihoods as what Participant 10 mentioned, *“Bale ang nangyari...syempre may proseso yan, interview muna kung talagang ako ay karapat-dapat. Kasi meron mga taong walang kakayahan...kailangan talagang i-evaluate. So, since nakita talaga na kailangan naman talaga ng mga kabuhayan dahil meron akong tatlong anak na nag-aaral at walang may hanapbuhay sa aming pamilya, ako ang naging kuwalipikado. Yun ang pinagpasimulan ko para ako magkaroon ng hanapbuhay.”* during the conduct of interview. The initiatives help the marginalized to identify suitable livelihoods for their needs, allot adequate

financial resources, support the community in development, and enhance the quality of life of these sectors.

In support, government agencies like Department of Agriculture and Cooperatives and Livelihood Development Department formulated different livelihood programs as what Participant 8 expressed, *“Pag ibinigay ang intervention, livelihood program ng LGU o di kaya ay national government Department of Agriculture, ipinamamahagi naman namin sa mga miyembro”*, Participant 4 explained, *“Nakikipagpartner si CLDD. Meron syang project kagaya ng rabbit production...so partnership with Department of Agriculture and CLDD with Sir Philip. So, pag nagseminar ka, meron kang trio...so ang nagbabayad doon ay CLDD tapos binibigay doon sa mga sineminar.”* which were distributed to cooperative members. These agencies improved the marginalized sectors’ access to economic opportunities, enhanced food stability, and provide income and employment.

Meanwhile, the implementation of livelihood program of government through **Livelihood Seminars** helped the marginalized sectors to participate and engage in livelihood opportunities as mentioned by Participant 7, *“Pinatutupad nila ito sa pamamagitan ng...yun nga pagcommunicate sa iba’t-ibang uri ng mga kababaihan, for example. And then through seminars din. Pag nakaattend ka po ng seminar regarding po dito. Yun yung nagstart ang implementation nila”* and Participant 2, *“Una yan inaanyayahan ka ng government...kung ikaw ay willing umattend ng seminars.”* which was revealed by the respondents. The livelihood seminars were pivotal in gaining valuable skills and knowledge in improving their livelihoods.

The government's efforts to reinforce different livelihood programs through livelihood seminars and initiatives influence the participation of the marginalized sectors. As these programs bring positive changes for the welfare of minorities, especially those who are economically weaker and deprived, step-by-step procedures and evaluations of possible beneficiaries are conducted. The selection process is based on their needs and knowledge of their livelihood. Through seminars and training, the marginalized sectors can gain ideas and knowledge on the program. These allow them to be more effective in improving their economic stability and strengthen their skills as livelihood beneficiaries.

Question 3: How do these livelihood programs provide opportunities to you and your family?

Theme C

Income and Agricultural Materials

With the theme, Income and Agricultural Materials, the marginalized participants expressed their experiences on livelihood opportunities provided to them and their family. These livelihoods opportunities came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

Providing **Extra Source of Income** to the families of marginalized sectors, the implementation of livelihood programs greatly helped their businesses to thrive and sustain their children’s expenses at school as what Participant 10 said, *“Kasi yung*

livelihood program na ipinagkaloob sa akin, that time lahat ng anak ko nag-aaral...so kailangan ko umisip kung saan ako kukuha ng pangaraw-araw naming pagkain, pambaon nila araw-araw. Alam ko na...na meron na akong pagkukuhanan. Nasa goal mo yan kung gusto mo maging maunlad ang negosyo mo syempre pagbutuhin para yung kita mo...yung pangangailangan ng pamilya mo, matustusan mo” and Participant 9, *“Malaking tulong yun samin dahil binigyan kami ng paunang yan para palaguin namin. Dyan po kami magsimula. Kung meron naman po kami ng dati, dagdag sa kabuhayan po.”* These livelihoods created network to support the participants monetarily and socially. The income from livelihoods fosters economic growth and financial security to the needs of marginalized sectors.

Meanwhile, the government provided **Aide for Farmers** through acquisition of agricultural materials, as mentioned by Participant 5, *“Okay naman po kasi...laking tulong na po yun kasi hindi na kami bibili tulad ng mga abono tsaka po mga buto. Kumbaga laking tulong na po yun kasi po sa taas po ng abono tsaka po mga buto. Mahal po kasi.”* as part of subsidy to small-scale farmers.

These livelihood opportunities are extended to the marginalized sectors’ families. The provision of livelihood enhances the chances of generating income and sustaining their needs. Since education plays a vital role in uplifting the situation of these marginalized sectors, they invest in the future of their children. This contributes to additional expenses for the family. Inasmuch, the income they acquire through livelihoods helps their children to continue their studies. Also, providing aid to the marginalized would lessen their expenses in agricultural materials. They could make use of their money for other necessities.

Question 4: What livelihood strategies have you adopted that improve your lives?

Theme D

Assistance, Adjustment, and Expansion Strategies

With the theme, Assistance, Adjustment, and Expansion Strategies, the marginalized participants described their adopted different livelihood strategies. These strategies came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

Through **Pieces of Livelihood Training and Seminars** as what Participant 8 mentioned, *“Katulad sa agrikultura...sa agrikultura kasi may mga trainings ang pagtanim. Although marunong na naman sila na magtanim, ay yun ay sinusupplement pa ng mga pag-aaral at trainings na binibigay samin ng LGU tsaka national government”* and Participant 6, *“Malaking naitutulong sakín ang mga trainings.”* where conducted to improve the marginalized sectors skills and knowledge on the livelihoods provided to them.

Meanwhile, the adjustment strategy in a form of **Hard work and Perseverance** was described by Participant 2, *“Pero napakalaking tulong kasi yun nga bawat bigay ng government pangalagaan mo kung anong meron ka para nagagamit mo habang nabubuhay ka. Yung mga strategies na natutunan ko dyan, dapat may pasensya ka, diba.*

Bawat ginagawa mo kailangan may pasensya ka. Sa pasensya mo dun ka magbubunga...kasi dun mo makikita yung pinagpasensyahan mo na ginagawa mo. Kasi kung wala kang pasensya at naiinis ka na...ano ba yan ayaw magbunga...ano ba yan nabulok, ganun natutunan ko...dapat may pasensya ka sa lahat ng ginagawa mo. At tsaka dapat masaya ka sa ginagawa mo” and Participant 7, *“Unang-una, kailangan ng sipag at pagtatyaga...yun yung unang-una na mai-aim mo sa...na para sa sarili mo. Kasi lahat naman ng bagay mahirap gawin so kailangan talaga ng dobleng sipag, dobleng pagtatyaga doon sa uri ng livelihood na gaganapin mo.”* helped improve their lives. The marginalized sectors considered these strategies in achieving their goals in life.

Additionally, **expansion of Income Creation, Networking, and Marketing** as were explained by Participant 1, *“...nagkaroon po kami ng extra income na makakatulong din po doon sa pagbabayad ng bills kasi po bawat gumagawa kami at nagti-train, kahit papaano may binibigay po silang honorarium at isa na rin po ako sa nagmamarket. Kahit papaano may percentage po kami”*, Participant 4 *“Next yung marketing naman. And hopefully magkaroon kami dito ng establishments, yung maluwang namin na lugar na yan is...paupahan namin sa mga gustong magtayo ng mga kainan”*, and Participant 10, *“...kapag pala ikaw may pangkabuhayan matututo kang makisama, magmanage...maliit man o malaki na business, matututo kang magmanage ng negosyo para maging maunlad, para mamonitor mo kung kumikita ka o hindi. Kung kailangan mo ba ng plan B mo para hindi mawala ang hanapbuhay na ipinagkaloob sayo. Para patuloy ang kita mo.”* developed their skills in marketing, create additional income to the family, and build linkages and networks.

The adopted strategies such as training and seminars help in improving their knowledge and skills. It also gives way for the marginalized sector to expand their linkages to possible customers of their products. The success of the business is through the effort and perseverance of the marginalized sectors. They value their hard work in improving their livelihoods no matter how small or large the business is. It also led them to be more creative and innovative to reach their target market. The creation of online marketing was one of the easy ways of distributing their products. It also helps them cope with different challenges.

Question 5: How do the skills acquired empower you as an individual?

Theme E

By Gaining Additional Knowledge and Skills

With the theme, *By Gaining Additional Knowledge and Skills*, the marginalized participants expressed the skills they have acquired that empowered them as individuals. These skills came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

The marginalized sectors emphasized the importance of skills acquired through **Livelihood Training and Seminars** in creating changes into their lives as mentioned by Participant 8, *“Sa pamamagitan ng pagsasanay, nadadagdagan ang aming kaalaman. Noong una konti lang ang kaalaman namin sa pag-aalaga ng baboy tsaka*

manok...ngayon alam na alam na namin. At sa pagtanim man, ganun din naman” and Participant 9, “Paraan ng pag-aalaga po ng mga hito. Kaya yun po ang lagi naming hinihingi na dumami pa ang mga seminar na aattendan kung paano po namin matututunan ang ganoong paraan at para lalong gumanda ang pag-aalaga.”

The livelihood training and seminars provided by the government improve their knowledge of different livelihood activities. Though small-scale farmers and fisherfolks have previous knowledge in farming, poultry-raising, and aquaculture, still, they are still looking forward to more seminars that will enhance their skills and abilities. Since the world is evolving, and many innovations are made to make work easier it will be an advantage for the marginalized workers to learn new things. These things will not only improve them as individuals but also empower them to aspire for a better life.

Question 6: How do the government strategies help you in measuring relevance and timeliness of livelihood programs being implemented?

Theme F

Availability, Reliability, and Technical Efficiency

With the theme, Availability, Reliability, and Technical Efficiency, the marginalized participants expressed how the government strategies helped their access to implemented livelihood programs. These government strategies came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

The application of **Acquired Knowledge and Skills through Availability of Training and Seminars** helped identify who were the target beneficiaries of the livelihood programs as what Participant 7 discussed, *“So ngayon, para sa akin malaking tulong yung kanilang strategy na naisip na yan kasi yung mga kagaya namin na individual natututo at the same time nakikinabang. Kumbaga yung mga programa ng gobyerno ay naibababa nila sa bawat indibidwal dito sa mga Calambeno. Masasabi kong maganda yung strategy na naisip nila na yung mga ganitong uri ng livelihood ay nare-reach out nila lalo na yung mga tao na nasa mga laylayan”* and Participant 8, *“Unang-una tinatanong nila kung sino ba ang mga interesado...mga prospective na magiging participant. Syempre yung mga participant ay interesado, may pagmamalasakit sa pagsasaka at livelihood. Kasi buhay na nila yan eh. At kapag nalaman ng gobyerno natin magse-set sila ng training, magcoconduct at ibigay naman nila saamin.”* revealed in an interview. These marginalized sectors described the government strategies as an effective way to reached and include them.

On the other hand, the importance of **Reliability to Government Support and Initiative** greatly influenced the success of the livelihood implemented as what Participant 2 explained, *“Nakatulong itong binibigay ng government, unang-una kasi biyuda ako. Syempre kapag biyuda ka, ang hanap mo, hanapbuhay talaga. Mapagkakakitaan para maitaguyod ang mga anak mo lalong-lalo na nung ang mga anak ko ay nagco-college. Malaking tulong sya kasi pandagdag kahit pamasaha. Kahit na walang meryenda basta may pamasaha sila. Yun ang malaking tulong na naibigay saakin”* and Participant 1, *“Ma’am, bale ang sa government namin ngayon very supportive lalo na po yung DA. Pag*

nagti-training po sila under ng sa mga gardening...bale sinasama po nila ang mushroom. At ang government ay nagsusupply naman po sila ng pangangailangan, kumbaga starter kit sa mga taong nag-aral ng training. At least meron po silang maumpisahan para po sa pangkabuhayan nila.” to sustain the marginalized sectors’ daily needs. The initiatives and support from the government, enabled the marginalized to maintain their livelihoods.

In like manner, **Technical Efficiency to Business Opportunities** created higher chances of success in livelihood as what Participant 10 discussed, *“Kumbaga yung isip ko na-open, nabukasan sa ganyang larangan na ang pagbubusiness, maliit man o malaki, talagang ano ka, kailangan mong maging ano sa Negosyo...matalino para hindi mawala yung binigay sayo.”* during the conduct of interview.

The government strategies allow the marginalized sectors to benefit economically and technically from business opportunities. It creates an impact on interested marginalized sectors to engage in livelihood activities. The training and seminars provided them with new ideas on how to sustain their livelihoods and the government support and initiatives allowed them to lessen their expenses in farming, fishing, and even in poultry production. The support enables them to access freely such materials needed in their livelihoods.

Question 7: How do these livelihood programs increase your profit in the market?

Theme G

Marketing and Financial Strategies

With the theme, Marketing and Financial Strategies, the marginalized participants emphasized how their profit increased in the market. These profit increment came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

The **Online Marketing, Unique Products, and Product Pricing** as what Participant 4 explained, *“Online marketing. Meron kami through ATI naman. So, tinuruan naman kami ng digital marketing pero syempre hindi naman ganun kalaki yung...more on kasi ito ng eco-farm. Eco-tourism farm. So, ang amin is a little of everything. Yung ano namin dito ay hindi talaga yung maximize farming o commercial farming”,* Participant 3, *“Sa pamamagitan ng harvest time, benebenta at ang iba pa pong mga kasamahan ay benebenta online.”*, Participant 1, *“Sa ngayon po, maganda naman ang naging impact. Isa na rin po ito sa nagiging...first na pangkabuhayan dito sa Calamba- ang mushroom.”*, and Participant 5, *“Sa merkado po hindi po yun katulad ng idadaan pa sa iba. Kaya yung price po nya nami-maintain po namin. Kaya malaking tulong po yung direkta na naidadala.”* have seen the potential of digital marketing in creating access to business opportunities, utilizing resources, opening of new perspectives and ideas, and controlling the business.

Meanwhile, the **Profit Gain** helped in sustaining the marginalized sectors business as what Participant 10 stated, *“May notebook kasi ako na sulatan, syempre may presyo yun na may tubo na tayo...hindi man mahal pero kikita tayo kasi pag sobrang mahal hindi*

tatangkilikin ng tao. Kung ang tubo mo naman ay hindi kalakihan pero mauubos din agad edi maganda ang pasok ng income sayo. Konti man pero mabilis ang benta” and Participant 7, “Karagdagan lang kasi yang kita...So malaking bagay kasi additional sya. For example, ito nga pong pag-aalaga ng sisiw, syempre may karagdagang kita dito eh...” could increase their profit.

Marketing strategies such as selling the products online, the uniqueness of products, and their price help the marginalized to thrive in business. In today’s era, livelihoods survive not only because of the large production of products but also because of the innovation of the business owners. Different platforms can be used to reach and offer the products to customers. The profit gain can help expand the business of the marginalized and create additional income for their families.

Question 8: How do these livelihood programs help yourself and your family?

Theme H

Personal and Financial Development

With the theme, Personal and Financial Development, the marginalized participants expressed how livelihoods help them and their families. The development came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

The **Personal Development through Personal Growth and Development and Improvement in Life** delved to the necessities of their families as what Participant 4 discussed, *“Kaya yung kita ko sa pagtanim, isi-save ko yun para yung expenses sa bahay at sa farm. Yung...yung income na yun nagagamit nila para sa mga pangangailangan sa bahay nila at sa farm. nakakatulong para mapaunlad ang kanilang pamumuhay pagdating sa farming”* and Participant 1, *“Noong una po dahil isa lang akong plain housewife, hindi po ako nakikisalamuha. Dahil po sa mga programa, nakishare po ako sa mga livelihood programs, unti-unti ko po nadevelop ang sarili ko.”* The development significantly affects the marginalized sectors’ status in their families and in community.

Furthermore, Participant 5 discussed the **Financial Gain** of the livelihood programs provided to them, *“Sa loob po ng isang araw nakakapag-apon...nakakapagtabi pa naman kahit papapano ng kaunting kita. Bukod po sa panggastos sa pang araw-araw ay yung ito naman, nakakapag-apon kami na naidadagdag namin...tulad ng nakapagpagawa po kami ng bahay. Tulong na rin po kaming mag-asawa bukod po sa kinikita sa gulay at sa pagtitinda, yun nakakaipon kami. Unti-unti namin napapagawa itong bahay.”* and Participant 7, *“Participant 7, “So ngayon ang masasabi ko lang dun na ang tagumpay eh yun nga nagkaroon ako ng additional income sa pamamagitan nito”, and Participant 8, “Unang-una, pag nakita kami nakita din ang miyembro. Nagkakaroon kami ng mga dibidendo.”* which helped the marginalized sectors to save money and improve their conditions in life.

Meanwhile, **Financial Aid for Education Expenses** assisted the children of marginalized as stated by Participant 10, *“Maliit man ang kinikita pero andun pa din ang puhunan ko...dun palang din alam kong may kikitain ako. Araw-araw na panggastos ng mga anak ko. Di naman puwedeng ang bata papasok sa school...Yun yung priority ko, at least kahit papaano ang baon nila doon na”*, Participant 9, *“Siguro po yung maitawid namin yung pang araw-araw namin at mapag-aral ko ang mga anak ko gamit ang pangkabuhayan na naibigay samin”*, Participant 3, *“Karagdagan lang kasi yang kita...So malaking bagay kasi additional sya. For example, ito nga pong pag-aalaga ng sisiw, syempre may karagdagan kita dito eh...”*, and Participant 2, *“Yung pinakatubo ang gawin mo wag mong kunin lahat, magtira ka rin para sa kapital para umunlad ng umunlad yung binigay sayo ng government na pangkabuhayan..maipagmamalaki ko kahit ako ay biyuda, nakapagtapos ang lima kong anak ng kanilang piniling kurso”*. It was audible to the marginalized sectors that the implementation of livelihoods greatly supported their children’s education and necessities in their homes. It became their source of living in times of crisis and tough situations.

Personal and financial development help the marginalized and their families earn additional income that they can use to save money, finance their children’s needs, and reconstruct their houses. Aside from income stability, the marginalized sectors develop their personal growth. Their livelihoods provide them chances to improve their lives, discover new skills, and unleash their full potential.

Question 9: What do you aspire/ wish to have in life?

Theme I

Sustainability of Livelihood Programs and Children’s Education

With the theme, Sustainability of Livelihood Programs and Children’s Education, the marginalized participants showed their aspirations in life. These aspirations came from their experiences or subordinate themes which were indicated in the succeeding paragraph.

The idea **To Pass on and Continue the Livelihood Programs to Future Generations**, as what Participant 1 mentioned, *“Unang-una ma’am syempre, hindi ko naman masasabi na habang panahon nandito ako. Ang inaano ko lang ma’am, lahat ng naturuan ko sana maging successful din sila at marating din po nila kung ano man ang narating ko ngayon. At sana naman po, ipapasa din po nila sa susunod na henerasyon at maging pakinabang din po sa susunod na kabataan”*, Participant 4, *“Yung matrain ang mga katulad nyo na kabataan, ma-equip kayo sa knowledge...iba kasi utak ng kabataan, para sila na magtutuloy. At mamotivate din kayo na hindi puwedeng mawala ang farmers”*, Participant 8, *“Dapat kahit hindi yung matatanda ngayon...dapat mamulat ang mga kabataan sa livelihood program na sinasabi. At sana magtuloy-tuloy na yang livelihood program na yan. Hindi naman masama yan, bagkus nakakabuti sa isang tao, isang pamilya na magkaroon ng livelihood activities”*, and Participant 2, *“Alam mo ang pinapangarap ko...sana ang tao matuto kung ano ang binigay ng gobyerno sayo. Sana yung mga taong binigyan ng livelihood, paunlarin nila, mahal in nila...kung ano ang binigay sa kanila ng government. Kasi minsan lang yan sa buhay eh. Hindi ka puwedeng*

umulit. Wag mong sayangin ang bawat biyayang ibinibigay sayo ng government.” aspired the marginalized sectors to ensure the balance and sustainability of livelihoods in long-term needs for future generations.

Additionally, the aspiration of **Wishing for their Children to Finish Studies** as what Participant 3 explained, *“Sana kahit ganito ang kabuhayan namin...sana makatapos ng pag-aaral ang aking mga anak”*, Participant 7, *“Wala ako masyadong winiwish. Ang gusto ko lang talaga makatapos ng pag-aaral ang mga anak ko. Yun lang”*, Participant 9, *“Sana tuloy tuloy itong ibinigay saamin na livelihood. Tsaka po sana yung mga anak ko mapagtapos ko kahit ito lang po ang hanapbuhay namin”*, and Participant 6, *“Simpleng buhay lang tsaka makatapos ang mga anak ko ng sa ganun may maganda silang kinabukasan.”* Aspired the marginalized to buy the things their children’s needs in school through the livelihood programs provided to them. It was because in the future, they wanted their children to have a better life. The investment to education elevated opportunities and transcend improvement and development to economic growth of the children of these sectors.

Sustaining the livelihood programs for the next generations created a positive impact on the lives of marginalized sectors and their children. In the future, these children would generate appropriate income opportunities to help improve their economic sufficiency, develop their self-reliance, and enhance their quality of life. Through this, aspiring for the marginalized sectors’ children to finish their education through livelihoods influenced their perception of life.

Summary of Findings

1. Level of Implementation of Different Livelihood Programs to Marginalized Sectors in terms of:

1.1 Applicability

It had a general assessment of 3.17 verbally interpreted as Implemented.

1.2 Acceptability

It had a general assessment of 3.21 verbally interpreted as Implemented.

1.3 Marketability

It had a general assessment of 3.15 verbally interpreted as Implemented.

1.4 Sustainability

It had a general assessment of 3.18 verbally interpreted as Implemented.

2. Life Satisfaction among Marginalized Sectors in terms of:

2.1 Life Satisfaction

It had a general assessment of 3.21 which was verbally interpreted as Satisfactory.

2.2 Affluent Life

It had a general assessment of 3.14 verbally interpreted as Satisfactory.

2.3 Rich Life Aspiration

It had a general assessment of 3.20 verbally interpreted as Satisfactory.

3. Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Livelihood Programs and the Level of Quality of Life among Marginalized Sectors in Calamba City.

There was a significant relationship between the level of implementation of livelihood programs and the level of quality of life among marginalized sectors in Calamba City. The interconnectedness of applicability to life satisfaction had .758, affluent life (.735), and rich life aspiration (.727). Meanwhile, acceptability to life satisfaction had .707, affluent life (.691), and rich life aspiration (.696). The marketability linked to life satisfaction had .721, affluent life (.699), and rich life aspiration (.742). Sustainability was related to life satisfaction which had .704, affluent life (.672), and rich life aspiration (.748). The level of significance was less than .05, thus, assessment of two groups of respondents had proved similar perspectives regarding the importance of livelihood to the economic improvement of marginalized sectors.

4. Lived Experience of the Participants from the Marginalized Sectors on the Implementation of Livelihood Programs and their Quality of Life.

The experience of marginalized sectors in accessing livelihood programs offered by the City Government greatly influenced their quality of life. It was reflected how livelihoods unfold different opportunities for them and their families as it created additional sources of income, improved their skills in farming, fishing, and poultry raising, developed their financial and personal growth, and helped them lessen their expenses in agricultural materials.

The initiatives of local government, cooperatives and associations, and the conduct of livelihood seminars intensified the promotion of combating poverty and inequality among marginalized sectors who have lesser access to opportunities and financial stability. Through this, various livelihood strategies have been adopted such as marketing, networking, technical efficiency, assistance, expansion, adjustment, reliability, availability, and financial strategy which improved the marginalized sectors' way of living. The livelihood approach provided solutions to the problems of marginalized sectors through creation of participatory and dynamic development opportunities for them.

This proved how the marginalized aspired for sustainable livelihood for future generations and continuous education of their children. These livelihoods not only reduce vulnerability but also secure income and necessities in life.

5. Proposed Livelihood Programs

Based on the result of the study, the proposed livelihood program for marginalized sectors entitled, "GADLiCAL Ni Rizal Program known as Gabay at Alalay sa Dalisay na Buhay gamit ang Livelihod para sa CALambuenos Ni Rizal" has its purpose of giving direct market to marginalized sectors' products in partnership with identified private sector/s through MoU. Also, the program aimed to provide win-win solutions to

beneficiaries' selling products and consumers' source of affordable yet fresh food at the table. This partnership would support the local farmers to grow their businesses and improve the local economy. It promoted efficiency where they could maximize their products with minimal costs. Besides, this approach would avoid the local farmers to compete with excessive importation of products in the market which was one of the main sources of hardships of marginalized sectors. Through 'gabay (guide) and alalay (support)', the Gender and Development Office would create linkages and assistance in a form of MoU, distribution of seeds, capital, and agricultural materials to marginalized sectors in Calamba. In this way, they could earn a living and sustain their livelihoods.

Conclusions

Based on the accumulated results, the following conclusions are made:

1. That livelihood programs offered by the City Government of Calamba in terms of applicability, acceptability, marketability, and sustainability were implemented. These livelihood programs are suitable to the needs of marginalized sectors as it provides technical and financial support for effective livelihoods, helps them adapt to different livelihood strategies, identifies the ideal program beneficiaries, draws attention to available goods and services, gains viable profits or income, and generated employment opportunities towards economic stability. It is also vital in coping with different shocks and stresses, enhancing skills, capabilities, and assets, and promoting active participation among marginalized sectors.
2. That the quality of life among marginalized sectors in terms of life satisfaction, affluent life, and rich life aspiration are satisfactory. Their satisfaction includes their capacity to work, personal relationships, good sleep, life stability, comfort, enjoyment, pleasantness, and the ability to create multiple streams of incomes. Through these ways, the marginalized sectors secure their necessities and improve their standard of living.
3. That implementation of livelihood programs and the quality of life significantly affect the economic security and wellbeing of marginalized sectors. The applicability, acceptability, marketability, and sustainability of livelihoods accessed by the marginalized sectors influence their life satisfaction, life affluence, and even their aspiration. It enhances their abilities and skills for personal and economic development.
4. That marginalized sectors' experiences on livelihood programs offered by the government show positive impacts in their lives. Their livelihoods enable them to support their children's education and other expenses. It allows them to be participative and efficient in different skills enhancement, improve their life conditions, and provide solutions for sustainable livelihoods to future generations.
5. That the proposed livelihood program was necessary to marginalized sectors as it would help them improve their marketing strategies when selling their products and/or

services. The program will serve as a linkage for stable income, help grow the marginalized sectors' businesses, and improve the local economy.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered:

1. The City Government may include the necessary livelihood programs based on the priority needs of marginalized sectors. It may observe proper allocation of fund and time frame of the program during planning and budgeting process. Since marketing of products is quite challenging for marginalized sectors, the government may introduce a program that will efficiently help them to connect directly to buyers. This approach may somehow provide them with a steady income and improve their life situations.

2. Implementers may conduct an intensive monitoring and evaluation to know the effectiveness of the program being implemented. They may identify issues and concerns, track improvements/progress, and measure the livelihood outcomes of marginalized sectors. With this process, the government may discern if the livelihoods create positive changes to the lives of marginalized, enhance their self-sufficiency, and secure holistic solutions to their necessities in life.

3. The implementers may engage the marginalized sectors in the discussion by providing solutions on how to market their products effectively. These marginalized sectors may act not only as beneficiaries but as participants of the program where they are included in decision-making. By empowering them, the government may provide appropriate income-generating opportunities and economic development for them.

4. Implementers may extend support or grant assistance to the children's beneficiaries to ensure their future through education. Though livelihoods allow the marginalized sectors to have food on the table and support the needs of the family through available funds, still, the income cannot meet the educational needs/ expenses of all their children. So, it is crucial that the government extends its support to the marginalized children to become economically resilient and help reduce vulnerabilities.

5. The City Government of Calamba may optimize the utilization of livelihood programs to help grow the marginalized sectors' businesses and provide financial independence. The assistance from the government may create equitable opportunities for marginalized to improve their capacities in the labor market.

6. Similar research may be conducted to further examine the issues and concerns about the implementation of livelihood as well as highlight its impact on people's lives.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical concerns were followed by the researcher as those were considered in this paper. Necessary letters of approval to conduct interviews and surveys with people

belonging to marginalized sectors in Calamba City were recorded. Through informed consent, disclosing of names and identities of participants and respondents was handled with utmost confidentiality to avoid and protect them from potential harm. The study had taken up respect for the privacy and autonomy of the respondents of the study. The duration and clear purpose of the research were also explained to the respondents.

Also, upon the approval of the questionnaire, it was distributed, and interviews were conducted with the participants. Honest and accurate interpretation of results from the questionnaires were tabulated, consolidated, analyzed, and interpreted. Statistical treatment was followed. The proper citations and acknowledgment were considered. Transparency of data results, methods, and procedures were also shown in the study.

Acknowledgments

Immense gratitude and appreciation to Almighty God, for the provision of grit during difficult circumstances that allows the researcher to finish her study; Mr. Alfredo G. Perez Jr., Dean, School of Graduate Studies, for his constructive criticisms, and unselfish advice for the betterment of this study; Dr. Ma. Lorena M. Tagala, Research Director, for her patience, technical expertise, and words of encouragement throughout the whole process of making this research meaningful; Dr. Chester Alexis C. Buama, Chairman of the Panelists, for his knowledge and suggestions that helped the researcher gather the necessary information needed in conducting this research; Dr. Marilyn L. Baysa, Research Adviser, for her unending support, guidance, and valuable comments and suggestions that help the researcher in the completion of this study; Allan Jay and Cassiopeia Oxygen, husband and daughter, for their tremendous support, understanding, and prayers that served as a driving force during the research process; Dr. Eulalia M. Javier, Quantitative Data Analyst, for her valuable advice and support in the analysis and interpretation of data; Mr. Ronel John E. Tarcilo, Qualitative Data Analyst, for his proofreading and summary of transcribed interviews of the participants; Laguna College of Business and Arts Faculty of Graduate Studies, for their good supervision, approachable staff, and adequate facilities during the conduct of the study; Ms. Jasmin P. Siman and Ms. Phoebe Cervantes, Validators, for their enthusiasm and desire to share their views and opinions for the improvement of the survey instrument; Sally Quilay, Agriculturist, for her unwavering help in identifying the needed respondents during the data gathering procedure; Gender and Development Personnel, for their understanding in preparing and distributing the questionnaires to target respondents; and, Respondents, for their precious time and effort to answer the survey questionnaires that serve a vital role in the success of this study.

REFERENCES

Abbadia, J. (2023, January 10). What is the role of Cronbach's Alpha and how do you interpret it? <https://mindthegraph.com/blog/cronbach-alpha/>

- Ames, H., Glenton, C., & Lewin, S. (2019). Purposive sampling in a qualitative evidence synthesis: a worked example from a synthesis on parental perceptions of vaccination communication. *National Library of Medicine National Center for Biotechnology Information*, 19(1):26. Doi 10.1186/s12874-019-0665-4
- Campbell, S. (2020). Purposive sampling: complex or simple? Research case examples. *National Library of Medicine. National Library of Medicine National Center for Biotechnology Information*, 25(8): 652-661. [https://doi: 10.1177/1744987120927206](https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206)
- De Castro, A.M. (2021). The Influence of Career Choice to Government Employees' Work Preference in Laguna: A Basis for Training Program. *Global Scientific Journals*, 9(7), 2320-9186.
- Draucker, C.B., Rawl, S., Vode, E., & Carter-Harris, L. (2020). Integration Through Connecting in Explanatory Sequential Mixed Method Studies. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 42(12):1137-1147. doi:10.1177/0193945920914647
- Foley Library Gonzaga University (2022, August 28). Mixed Methods Research. <https://researchguides.gonzaga.edu/qualitative/mixed-methods>
- National Economic Development Authority (NEDA) (2016, July 24). 2016 Annual Report. <https://neda.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/AR-JULY-24-for-website.pdf>
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022, August 11). What is Purposive Sampling? Definition and Examples. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/author/kassianin/page/11/#:~:text=Published%20on%20August%2011%2C%202022,on%20purpose%E2%80%9D%20in%20purposive%20sampling.>
- Othman, S., Steen, M., & Fleet, J.A. (2020). A sequential explanatory mixed methods study design: An example of how to integrate data in a midwifery research project. *Journal of Nursing and Practice*, 11(2):75. DOI: 10.5430/jnep.v11n2p75
- Sackey, P.K. & Remoaldo, P. (2019). Ghana's Livelihood Empowerment Against Poverty (LEAP) programme is leaking: Irregularities watering down the impact of the flagship LEAP programme. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 5:1. DOI: 10.1080/23311886.2019.1627789
- Staller, K.M. (2020). Big enough? Sample in qualitative inquiry. *Sage Journals Qualitative Social Work*, 20(4), 897-904. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14733250211024516>
- Tarcilo, R.J. (2022). Breakthrough In Telepsychology: Pandemic-Based Experience of Psychologists
- Wokadala, J., Ssesanga, A., & Akampwera, H. (2020). Effectiveness of the Public Livelihood Programmes on the demand for education, health, and water services in Uganda: A case for sustainable pilot. *Advances in Economics and Business*, 8(4), 243-253. doi:10.13189/aeb.2020.080405
-